

MONO-BIGUANIDE AND HETEROCHELATE COPPER COMPLEXES

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The isolation of two series of entirely new types of 4-co-ordinated copper complex, in the pure state, has been described. These are of the type $[(X)_2.Cu.(A)]$ and $[(B).Cu.(A)]$ where A and B represent molecules of two different bifunctional ligands, and X is a neutral molecule like H_2O or a negatively charged ion like Cl^- or $\frac{1}{2}SO_4^{2-}$. The mono-biguanide and glycine-biguanide complexes of copper represent these two interesting types of four co-ordination compounds.

The constitution of these compounds has been discussed in the light of their physical and chemical properties including a study of their magnetic susceptibilities and absorption spectra.

While examining the validity of Bjerrum's stepwise dissociation theory (Bjerrum, "Metalamine formation in aqueous solution", P. Haase & Son, Copenhagen, 1941) in the case of inner-metallic complexes of the third order (cf. Ray and Dutt, this *Journal*, 1948, 25 564), it was observed that the 4-co-ordinated copper biguanides exhibited a very interesting phenomenon. The violet colour of the copper-bis-biguanide complexes in aqueous solution was found to change gradually to deep blue with progressive addition of an acid, while an excess of the acid destroyed the deep colour, the solution attaining the faint greenish blue tinge of the hydrated copper ion. This colour change may be explained on the basis of stepwise decomposition as follows :—

where $BigH$ = one molecule of biguanide = $C_2N_3H_7$

The deep blue colour developed in acid solution invariably indicates the appearance of a new entity, presumably a copper *mono*-biguanide complex.

From the physico-chemical studies (to be communicated shortly) of the bivalent metal biguanide complexes in aqueous acid solution, it was evident that the *mono*-biguanide complexes are more stable in acid solutions than their corresponding *bis*-biguanide analogues, particularly the complex copper compounds. The fact that nickel *bis*-biguanide complexes do not exhibit such colour transitions in aqueous acid solution can be explained on the basis that nickel *mono*-biguanide complexes, if at all formed, are not appreciably more stable than their *bis*-biguanide analogues. The nickel biguanide complexes in general were also found to be less stable than the corresponding complexes of copper.

The isolation of a number of the intermediate, apparently co-ordinatively unsaturated copper *mono*-biguanide complexes in the pure solid state, under controlled pH values of the solution, has been described in the present paper. This undoubtedly confirms the validity of Bjerrum's (*loc. cit.*) stepwise dissociation theory so far as it refers to the case of bi-positive copper biguanide complexes.

In the chemistry of four-co-ordinated complexes no compound has been described in literature where different chelate molecules are associated with a single metal ion.

to yield a mixed inner complex of the type

usually the type $[MA_2]$ or $[MB_2]$ are formed where A and B are bifunctional groups like dimethylglyoxime, hydroxyaldehydes, diamines, α -dipyridyl, β -ketonic esters, biguanides, amidines and the like.

With the isolation of *mono*-biguanides of copper, which may be represented on the basis of Werner's theory as diaquo- or dichloro-complexes of the type

where A is a bidentate ligand and X, a neutral molecule like H_2O or a univalent negative ion like Cl^- , the possibility of preparing four-covalent heterochelate complexes of copper of the type

with A and B as both bifunctional but different ligands, suggested itself. Loss of symmetry and steric hindrances that may arise therefrom are, however, likely to increase the instability of such complexes, rendering them often incapable of isolation in the pure state.

A suitable chelating molecule, which is known to form characteristic copper complex of the inner-metallic type, is found in the α -amino-acids. The acid decomposition constants of copper *mono*-biguanide and *mono*-glycine were found on examination to be almost equal in magnitude.

Hence, it was reasonably expected that glycine and other lower members of the α -amino-acid series might favourably occur together with biguanide in a heterochelate complex. This has indeed been realised in the present case of copper-biguanide amino-acid complexes.

The *mono*-biguanide and heterochelate copper complexes represent entirely new types of co-ordination compounds in as much as the essential symmetry attainable with two identical bidentate chelates breaks down in these cases. It was, therefore, considered interesting to measure the magnetic susceptibility and determine the absorption spectra of these compounds with a view to establish their nature.

Susceptibility measurements were made in a Gouy's balance with field strength of 9.36×10^3 gauss. The results show that the *mono*-biguanide complexes have a comparatively low moment value of 1.75-1.81 than the glycine-biguanide complexes (1.83-1.94). With ~~co~~-rection this difference might have possibly been more or less rigidly defined.

It may, therefore, be tentatively suggested that the *mono*-biguanide copper complexes are of the penetration class with dsp^3 hybrid bonds, while the glycine-biguanide complexes belong to the associated type with sp^3d hybrid bonds resonating with ionic ones.

The absorption spectrum of the copper *mono*-biguanide chloride together with those of *bis*-biguanide chloride and copper chloride shows that a definitely new species of co-ordination complex has been formed in the case of the *mono*-biguanide compounds

FIG. 1

FIG. 2

FIG. 3

Fig 1. Solution taken in a Baly's tube ; thickness of the liquid column = 30 mm. exposure = 25 seconds.

- (a) and (f), iron arc.
- (b) Copper *bis*-biguanide chloride ($M/20$) ; absorption in the region 5688 Å to 4600 Å and beyond 4000 Å.
- (c) Copper chloride ($M/20$) ; absorption beyond 4000 Å.
- (d) Copper *mono*-biguanide chloride ($M/10$) ; absorption above 5700 Å.
- (e) Mixtures of equal volumes of copper chloride ($M/10$) and copper *bis*-biguanide chloride ($M/10$) ; absorption in the same region as in (d), but less pronounced.

Fig. 2. Solution taken in a double compartment cell.

(a), (b) and (c) refer to copper *mono*-biguanide ($M/20$) in both compartments ; time of exposure is 40, 30, and 20 sec. in (a), (b) and (c) respectively.

Absorption above 5700 Å in (a) and above 5600 Å in (b) and (c).

Copper *bis*-biguanide chloride ($M/20$) in one compartment & copper chloride in the other. Time of exposure is 20, 30 & 40 sec. in (d), (e) and (f) respectively.

Absorption in the region, 5670 to 4600 Å.

Fig 3. Solution taken in a Baly's tube. Thickness = 30 mm. Exposure = 20 sec

- (a) and (f), iron arc.
- (b) Copper *bis*-biguanide chloride ($M/20$) ; absorption in the region, 5688 to 4600 Å, and 5870 to 5700 Å (slight)
- (c) Copper glycine ($M/20$) ; absorption beyond 4150 Å and above 5700 Å.
- (d) Copper glycine-biguanide chloride ($M/10$) ; absorption above 4800 Å and beyond 4150 Å.
- (e) Mixtures of equal volumes of copper glycine ($M/10$) and copper *bis*-biguanide chloride ($M/10$) ; absorption same as in (d) but less pronounced.

(cf. Figs. 1 and 2.). It is formed in appreciable quantities by mixing the latter two salts in molecular proportions. The alternative method of representing them as copper bis-biguanide cuprichloride or molecular compounds of copper bis-biguanide chloride and copper chloride is hereby excluded. The preparation of a series of salts of the mono-biguanide copper complex is an additional evidence in support of this view.

The case of copper glycine-biguanide chloride is somewhat different in as much as the absorption spectrum of this compound seems to some extent to be due to the superimposition of the absorption bands of copper bis-biguanide chloride and copper-glycine. This indicates that the compound may as well be a weak complex of the associated type, or a mere double compound, as is supported by magnetic data. But, the isolation of a number of halide salts like chloride, bromide, iodide, etc, its low solubility, and its stability in aqueous solution permitting recrystallisation from hot water, appear to militate against that view.

EXPERIMENTAL

Copper Mono-biguanide Chloride.—Copper bis-biguanide (1 g.) was dissolved in 20 c.c. of hot water and treated dropwise with dilute hydrochloric acid (1:4) till a deep blue coloured solution was obtained with a f_{max} value of 3.5-4.5. This was filtered and allowed to crystallise in the cold. Shining deep blue crystals of the copper mono-biguanide chloride separated. The crystals were washed with small portions of cold water (containing 1 c.c. of 0.1 M-HCl per litre) and dried in air. The substance suffers dismutation in aqueous solution with the formation of bis-biguanide complex (*vide infra*), but can be recrystallised from hot dilute hydrochloric acid (0.001M). {Found: Cu, 23.46; N, 25.90; Cl, 26.19; H₂O (by loss of weight at 105°), 13.24. [Cu(BigH)]Cl₂, 2H₂O requires Cu, 23.50; N, 25.87; Cl, 26.25; H₂O, 13.36 per cent}. where BigH=one mol. of biguanide=C₂N₃H₇.

Copper Mono-methylbiguanide Chloride.—Copper bis-methylbiguanide chloride (1 g.) was dissolved in 20 c.c. of water by heating on the water-bath. The deep red-violet solution was mixed with a solution of copper chloride (0.5 g. in 5 c.c. water). This was then treated dropwise with 5 c.c. of hydrochloric acid (0.1 M). The deep blue solution was concentrated on the water-bath to about 20 c.c. and then filtered hot. The product, which separated on cooling, was recrystallised from hot dilute hydrochloric acid (p_{H} 3-5) and the deep blue crystals were washed and dried as before. {Found: Cu, 25.63; N, 28.15; Cl, 28.50. [Cu (Me-BigH)] Cl₂ requires Cu, 25.45; N, 28.05; Cl, 28.45 per cent} where Me-BigH=one molecule of methylbiguanide=CH₃.C₂N₃H₆.

Copper mono-methylbiguanide sulphate was prepared like the previous compound using the corresponding sulphates and sulphuric acid in place of chloride and hydrochloric acid. The shining blue crystals decompose in water with the separation of red-violet copper bis-methylbiguanide sulphate and the formation of copper sulphate by dismutation. {Found: Cu, 20.50; N, 22.39; SO₄, 30.89; H₂O (by loss of wt. at 105°), 11.70. [Cu(Me-BigH)]SO₄.2H₂O requires Cu, 20.45; N, 22.54; SO₄, 30.91; H₂O, 11.60 per cent}.

Copper mono-ethylbiguanide chloride was prepared in a similar manner from copper bis-ethylbiguanide chloride, copper chloride, and hydrochloric acid and recrystallised

from dilute hydrochloric acid (p_H 3-4) as deep blue shining crystals. {Found: Cu, 23.40; N, 25.82; Cl, 26.07. $[\text{Cu}(\text{Et-BigH})]\text{Cl}_2 \cdot 0.5\text{H}_2\text{O}$ requires Cu, 23.33; N, 25.73; Cl, 26.09 per cent}.

Copper mono-dimethylbiguanide chloride was prepared following the same procedure as given above from the corresponding *bis*-biguanide chloride. It forms deep blue crystals. {Found: Cu, 23.24; N, 25.80; Cl, 26.06. $[\text{Cu}(\text{Me}_2\text{-BigH})]\text{Cl}_2 \cdot 0.5\text{H}_2\text{O}$ requires Cu, 23.33; N, 25.73; Cl, 26.09 per cent}.

Copper mono-dimethylbiguanide sulphate was prepared in the same way as the complex chloride under controlled p_H (3-4) by adding a suitable quantity of dilute sulphuric acid (25 c.c. of 0.1 $N\text{-H}_2\text{SO}_4$) to a solution of the *bis*-dimethylbiguanide copper sulphate (2 g.) and copper sulphate (1 g.). The substance forms fine blue crystalline powder. {Found: Cu, 21.24; N, 23.58; SO_4 , 32.60. $[\text{Cu}(\text{Me}_2\text{-BigH})]\text{Cl}_2 \cdot 0.5\text{H}_2\text{O}$ requires Cu, 21.34; N, 23.53; SO_4 , 32.28 per cent}.

Copper Mono-diethylbiguanide Chloride.—Copper *bis*-diethylbiguanide chloride under similar treatment as in the previous cases yielded this compound as a blue powder. This was washed and dried as usual. {Found: Cu, 21.24; N, 23.36; Cl, 23.73. $[\text{Cu}(\text{Et}_2\text{-BigH})]\text{Cl}_2 \cdot 0.5\text{H}_2\text{O}$ requires Cu, 21.13; N, 23.39; Cl, 23.63 per cent}.

Copper Glycine-biguanide Chloride.—Copper *bis*-biguanide chloride (3.7 g.) was dissolved in warm water (20 c.c.) and the solution was treated with a mixture of copper chloride (1.7 g.) and glycine (1.5 g.) in solution. The deep blue solution was filtered and the filtrate was concentrated on the water-bath to half its original volume. On cooling, deep blue-violet crystals separated out. The product was recrystallised from hot water and dried in air. {Found: Cu, 21.19; N, 28.02; Cl, 11.85. $\left[\begin{array}{c} (\text{C}_2\text{N}_5\text{H}_7) \\ \text{Cu} \\ (\text{C}_2\text{NO}_2\text{H}_4) \end{array} \right] \text{Cl} \cdot 1.5\text{H}_2\text{O}$ requires Cu, 21.10; N, 27.91; Cl, 11.80 per cent}.

Copper Glycine-biguanide Bromide.—To a hot solution of copper glycine-biguanide chloride (1g. in 50 c.c. water), a solution of potassium bromide (1 g. in 10 c.c. water) was added. The solution was warmed for a few minutes and then filtered hot. The filtrate, on cooling, deposited the fine blue-violet crystals of the complex bromide. This was recrystallised from hot water containing a little bromide and dried in air. {Found: Cu, 18.00; N, 23.70. $\left[\begin{array}{c} (\text{C}_2\text{N}_5\text{H}_7) \\ \text{Cu} \\ (\text{C}_2\text{NO}_2\text{H}_4) \end{array} \right] \text{Br} \cdot 2\text{H}_2\text{O}$ requires Cu, 17.92; N, 23.70 per cent}.

Copper glycine-biguanide iodide was prepared from a slightly ammoniacal solution of copper glycine-biguanide chloride with potassium iodide. The product was recrystallised from hot water containing a drop of ammonia. It forms dark blue-violet crystals. {Found: Cu, 16.59; N, 22.00. $\left[\begin{array}{c} (\text{C}_2\text{N}_5\text{H}_7) \\ \text{Cu} \\ (\text{C}_2\text{NO}_2\text{H}_4) \end{array} \right] \text{I} \cdot \text{H}_2\text{O}$ requires Cu, 16.56; N, 21.91 per cent}.

Copper Alanine-biguanide Chloride.—Copper *bis*-biguanide chloride (3.7 g.), copper chloride (1.7 g.) and alanine (1.8 g.) were dissolved in water (200 c.c.). The solution was concentrated on the water-bath when blue-violet crystals began to separate. The mixture was cooled; the product obtained was purified by recrystallisation from hot water containing a little potassium chloride. {Found: Cu, 18.64; N, 24.59; Cl, 10.43.

$\left[\begin{array}{c} (\text{C}_2\text{N}_5\text{H}_7) \\ \text{Cu:} \\ (\text{C}_3\text{NO}_2\text{H}_4) \end{array} \right] \text{Cl}, 3\text{H}_2\text{O}$ requires Cu, 18.57; N, 24.57; Cl, 10.28 per cent} where $\text{C}_3\text{NO}_2\text{H}_4 = 1$ molecule of alanine.

Copper glycine-methylbiguanide chloride was prepared following the same procedure as in the case of the copper glycine-biguanide chloride. The product forms deep blue-violet crystals. {Found: Cu, 21.42; N, 28.32; Cl, 12.01. $\left[\begin{array}{c} (\text{C}_3\text{N}_5\text{H}_8) \\ \text{Cu} \\ (\text{C}_2\text{NO}_2\text{H}_4) \end{array} \right] \text{Cl}, 0.5 \text{H}_2\text{O}$ requires Cu, 21.38; N, 28.28; Cl, 11.95 per cent}.

Copper glycine-ethylbiguanide chloride was prepared as described in the previous case using copper bis-ethylbiguanide chloride and glycine. {Found: Cu, 20.51; N, 27.14; Cl, 11.43. $\left[\begin{array}{c} (\text{C}_4\text{N}_5\text{H}_{11}) \\ \text{Cu:} \\ (\text{C}_2\text{NO}_2\text{H}_4) \end{array} \right] \text{Cl}, 0.5\text{H}_2\text{O}$ requires Cu, 20.42; N, 27.01; Cl, 11.41 per cent}.

Copper alanine-ethylbiguanide chloride was prepared exactly in the same way as the previous compound using alanine in place of glycine. It forms deep blue-violet crystals. {Found: Cu, 18.11; N, 23.98; Cl, 10.14. $\left[\begin{array}{c} (\text{C}_4\text{N}_5\text{H}_{11}) \\ \text{Cu} \\ (\text{C}_2\text{NO}_2\text{H}_4) \end{array} \right] \text{Cl}, 2\text{H}_2\text{O}$ requires Cu, 18.04; N, 23.86; Cl, 10.09 per cent}.

All these compounds can also be prepared from the corresponding *mono*-biguanide copper complex (1 mol.) and glycine or alanine (1 mol.) in aqueous ammonia solution at a p_{H} of about 6-7. No heterochelate complex with anions other than the halides could, however, be prepared.

TABLE I

Magnetic susceptibilities of mono-biguanide and heterochelate copper complexes.

Substance	Temp.	$\chi_{\text{g}} \times 10^6$	$\chi_{\text{M}} \times 10^6$	Diamag. correc. $\times 10^6$	$\chi_{\text{A}} \times 10^6$	μ_{B}
1. $[\text{Cu}(\text{MeBigH})]\text{Cl}_2$	24°	4.789	1195	104	1299	1.77
2. $[\text{Cu}(\text{MeBigH})]\text{SO}_4 \cdot 2\text{H}_2\text{O}$	27°	3.993	1240	118	1358	1.81
3. $[\text{Cu}(\text{MeBigH})]\text{SO}_4$	28°	4.498	1235	97	1332	1.80
4. $[\text{Cu}(\text{EtBigH})]\text{Cl}_2 \cdot 0.5\text{H}_2\text{O}$	32°	4.110	1120	121	1241	1.75
5. $[\text{Cu}(\text{Me}_2\text{BigH})]\text{SO}_4 \cdot 0.5\text{H}_2\text{O}$	32.5°	4.381	1194	121	1315	1.80
6. $[\text{Cu}(\text{Me}_2\text{BigH})]\text{SO}_4 \cdot 0.5\text{H}_2\text{O}$	33°	3.950	1173	114	1287	1.78
7. $[\text{Cu}(\text{Et}_2\text{BigH})]\text{Cl}_2 \cdot 0.5\text{H}_2\text{O}$	24°	4.003	1203	137	1337	1.79
8. $\left[\begin{array}{c} (\text{BigH}) \\ \text{Cu} \\ (\text{Glyc}) \end{array} \right] \text{Cl}, 1.5\text{H}_2\text{O}$	24°	4.822	1442	121	1563	1.96
9. $\left[\begin{array}{c} (\text{BigH}) \\ \text{Cu} \\ (\text{Glyc}) \end{array} \right] \text{Br}, 2\text{H}_2\text{O}$	32°	3.502	1238	126	1364	1.83
10. $\left[\begin{array}{c} (\text{BigH}) \\ \text{Cu} \\ (\text{Alan}) \end{array} \right] \text{Cl}, 3\text{H}_2\text{O}$	32°	4.261	1453	160	1613	1.99
11. $\left[\begin{array}{c} (\text{EtBigH}) \\ \text{Cu} \\ (\text{Glyc}) \end{array} \right] \text{Cl}, 0.25\text{H}_2\text{O}$	32°	4.730	1471	134	1605	1.99
12. $\left[\begin{array}{c} (\text{MeBiH}) \\ \text{Cu} \\ (\text{Glyc}) \end{array} \right] \text{Cl}, 0.5\text{H}_2\text{O}$	32°	4.101	1218	117	1335	1.83

Where BigH = one mol. of biguanide base = $\text{C}_3\text{N}_5\text{H}_7$; GlycH = $\frac{1}{2}$ mol. of glycine = $\text{C}_2\text{NO}_2\text{H}_4$.
 AlanH = one mol. of alanine = $\text{C}_3\text{NO}_2\text{H}_7$.

Absorption Spectra.—The absorption spectrograms of the *mono*-biguanide and glycine-biguanide copper complex in aqueous solution were taken by means of a glass-prism spectroscope, the light source being an incandescent lamp, with iron arc as reference.

The data below the figures summarise the experimental details and results.

DISCUSSION

The copper *mono*-biguanide complexes, in the solid hydrated state or in aqueous solution, occur presumably as diaquo-copper biguanide salts in agreement with the maximal or characteristic co-ordination number four of copper, on the basis of Werner's theory. In their anhydrous or dehydrated form, they obviously change into the dichloro compounds, which would have been a non-electrolyte if it could exist unchanged in aqueous solution. This is evident from the following formulae :—

Even in the diaquo-form (I), represented as an electrolyte or salt, the substance suffers dismutation in aqueous solutions giving the stable copper *bis*-biguanide chloride and copper chloride :

while the dichloro compound (II) in aqueous solution changes immediately into the diaquo-form, which then suffers dismutation as shown above.

The deep blue *mono*-biguanide complexes might as well be represented as a compound of the type :

where X = Cl, Br, I or $\frac{1}{2}\text{SO}_4$ (cf. Chattaway and Drew, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1937, 947).

The partial formation of the blue compound from the *bis*-biguanide copper complex and the simple copper salt appears to justify this suggestion to a certain degree. But their solubility with reference to those of their components fails to exhibit any additivity relation. Then again, it has been shown from physical measurements (to be communicated hereafter) that even at dilutions where the formation of any anionic complex like $[\text{CuX}_4]^-$ is out of question, the colour of an acidified copper *bis*-biguanide salt is blue, which corresponds to the formation of *mono*-biguanide complexes. Furthermore, all attempts to prepare blue compounds of the type $[\text{Cu}\{\text{C}_2\text{H}_4(\text{BigH})_2\}][\text{CuX}_4]$ from a copper ethylenedibiguanide chloride, $[\text{Cu}\{\text{C}_2\text{H}_4(\text{BigH})_2\}]\text{Cl}_2$, and copper chloride, CuCl_2 , even in the presence of hydrochloric acid ended in failures, the formation of *mono*-biguanide being impossible, as ethylenedibiguanide represents a quadri-dentate ligand. The blue compounds are therefore represented as *mono*-biguanide complexes.

The mixed or heterochelate copper complexes cannot also be regarded as mere double or molecular compounds of copper *bis*-biguanide salts with copper-glycine or copper-alanine. Their stability in aqueous solutions from which they can be recrystallised unchanged, their preparation in the form of a series of halide salts, furnish sufficient evidences in support of their figuring as heterochelate complexes.

In acid solutions it may, however, lead to a dismutation equilibrium as

Investigation into the mechanism of decomposition of copper glycine-biguanide chloride in aqueous acid solution, which may be represented as,

leads to no definite result, except that the first decomposition process gives a constant of the order of 10^3 , being the same as that of copper *bis*-biguanide complexes. But the second decomposition process, which should be identical with the decomposition constant of copper *mono*-biguanide or copper *mono*-glycine, gives a somewhat lower value than either.

This apparent discrepancy may be explained on the supposition that the two processes (I) and (II) occur simultaneously, which is quite probable in the light of the fact that the decomposition constant of copper *mono*-biguanide and copper *mono*-glycine are almost nearly equal. The process is also complicated due to the dismutation reactions stated above.